

Work Hard MAVE Hard: Live from the 2024 Mutational Scanning Symposium

Episode 4 Transcript

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Facilitated by the Atlas of Variant Effect Alliance

[Intro music plays]

Alex Nguyen Ba: Welcome back to the Variants and Us Podcast for an exclusive special report. Joining us live from Boston, Evelina from our team is on site at the Mutational Scanning Symposium at the Broad Institute. Kortni is with me in the studio to help with this special episode. Evelina, how is the atmosphere there? Is there a lot of excitement?

Evelina Tronina: There is definitely a lot of excitement. I think I saw about a hundred scientists that apparently have flown in from all over the world. Right now, the hosts are setting up the conference room and the poster boards, and I saw some very familiar names like Doug Fowler, Fritz Roth, and many others!

Kortni Kindree: What do you think they'll be talking about? Will there be a new gene with a variant effect map? Or maybe a new technique will be introduced?

Evelina: Absolutely, I think all of this will be happening at this symposium. In the agenda for the meeting there were talks about machine learning, new consortiums for genetic panels, and so on. Oh my god, is that Adrine? You can't see this, but I think that's Adrine in the background. Hold on, I'm going to go interview her.

Alex: Actually, Kortni have you seen Adrine lately? Is that where she is right now? Is she on vacation?

Kortni: Actually yeah, I haven't seen her lately!

Evelina: It's definitely her. Can you please introduce yourself and give us a background on your career?

Adrine de Souza: My name is Adrine de Souza. I am from Brazil. I'm a biotechnologist by training and I'm also involved in the Variant Effect Seminar Series and the Variants and Us podcast. So, yay, I'm here! And, my background is that I did work along with molecular biology and I knew that I want to work with human genetics.

Evelina: And what made you interested in this field?

Adrine: I knew that I wanted to work with rare diseases. So I end up in Boston University working in FOP, a rare disease that people grow bone instead of muscles. And I work in this, like, pathway and using other drugs that are already approved to try to make that better. And now I'm working in variant interpretation large scale for genes that are involved in kidney disease. And what made me interested in MAVEs, I would say that's mainly my PI that introduced me to this field. But I also think it has a big potential to truly study a small region of the genome. Like I know, it's a small but it's still, it's very deep understanding of the small region of the genome. So it's a very tiny but important contribution to the atlas of variant effects.

Evelina: So what are some of the recent things you have explored?

Adrine: So I said that I work in FOP, I also work with the gene called HL that causes this familial cancer, like renal cancer and also somatic renal cancer. I did also start working with like technology development. I was trying to make higher order genetic interactions technology a thing with a multiplex CRISPR that would target seven genes at a time, but it didn't quite work. [laughs] But I'm really happy where I landed, I'm working mostly in the clinical side of variant interpretation and variant effects.

Evelina: Do you think we'll be able to solve all of these problems in the next ten years?

Adrine: I think that in ten years from now, we will have variant effect predictors that are going to be much better than our experimental data. And maybe we will start seeing this type of variant effective predictors also being good at contextual like drug-based cell-type specific predictions. So I really hope that there's a thing that happens, so we don't have to test everything in every condition.

Evelina: Nice! Now I'm going to ask you a very serious question... what's the stupidest thing you've done in the lab?

Adrine: Well, I did forget to properly close the ultracentrifuge lid and it was crazy, gave me PTSD for life. It made a, made a smoke smell but it was fine, nothing exploded. It was just a bad centrifuge for a little while. [both laugh]

Evelina: And what about the smartest thing?

Adrine: And I'll say I did do some very smart things in the lab, like being able to use a multichannel to load gels. But I'll say that mentoring students are the most smartest thing in the lab.

Evelina: Nice, multiplexing gels! What else would you multiplex with all of your intelligence?

Adrine: And I really wish that I could multiplex outside of the lab, its writing papers. But we cannot use AI for that, so not yet.

Evelina: Oh man, one day. Thanks Adrine! I should probably get back to the report.

Alex: Actually, that sounded pretty fun and informative. Why don't you just try and get other people's perspectives? I think a lot of our listeners here will want to get a feel for how the symposium is going.

Evelina: Ok! Let me see. Oh I see over there Dr. Buchser over there, let me go over there and talk to him. Hi! Can you give us some background on your career and introduce yourself?

Willie Buchser: I was a music major and I decided that it was easy to do music part-time rather than full-time, and I switched into neuroscience. And so now I'm a genetics professor at WashU at the MGI, the McDonald Genome Institute.

Evelina: And what made you interested in MAVEs?

Willie: We didn't know they were called MAVEs at the time. We've been screening neurons and cancer since 2006, and when the ability after CRISPR came out, the ability to do it pooled was of course, life changing. And so really, you know, right away as soon as it became a possibility, we wanted to turn our arrayed screens into cold screens.

Evelina: Talking about how life-changing this was, where do you see the MAVE field going in the next ten years?

Willie: Yeah, I think we're going to be able to use it for therapeutics more directly you at that time. So rather than right now, a lot of it is to figure out what's the problem, what mutations cause a problem, but to directly figure out what things can give us the solution to a problem. So where I really want it to be is, you know, a patient comes in their genome is sequenced. We apply a MAVE like assay to all of that patients, that single n of one patient's variants across the entire genome.

And then we say this is what's causing your disease, now we can make the correct CRISPR to go in and correct it.

Evelina: In the meantime though, what's something that you hope that won't have to do again in the next ten years?

Willie: I have juggled glass labware.

Evelina: Of course, of course.

Willie: Amazingly, the smaller labware doesn't break so easily because they were beakers. But people convinced me to do the larger stuff and then that went poorly.

Evelina: Thank you and enjoy the rest of the conference!

Kortni: Evelina, we are loving the interviews back at the studio! Let's see how many more people you can interview before the next session starts.

Evelina: I managed to find Justin Kinney as you were saying that. Justin, can you introduce yourself?

Justin: I'm an associate professor at Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory. I am actually a physicist by training I started out graduate school doing string theory. But midway through graduate school, I switched to biophysics because I, you know, I was really excited about the possibility of working in a field where I can make theoretical predictions and then test those predictions in the lab myself. So, after a while doing computational biology, I became really inspired by some work from Barack Cohen's lab and also the recently developed high-throughput sequencing methods. So I told my advisor in my last year of graduate school, I wanted to start doing experiments. And this is right before my sixth year began.

Evelina: That's an interesting time to start doing experiments. Actually, Alex back home has a similar path and now he just does experiments to escape grading essays. But anyways, what did you study?

Justin: So the idea I had was I was interested in the mechanisms of gene regulation. Specifically, the biophysical mechanisms like actually trying to measure interaction energies between proteins in living cells. So, you know, I realized that with high-throughput sequencing and fluorescence activated cell sorting, we could measure gene expression from very large numbers of variant transcription regulatory sequences. And so I went the lab, I created this method demonstrated and this turned out to be, you know, one of the first MAVES.

Evelina: I noticed your talk title mentioned something in this area, is that right?

Justin: Well, we're using massively parallel assays in the context of splicing to try to understand how splice modifying drugs work. Splice modifying drugs are a relatively new type of therapeutic. They've had spectacular success for treating spinal muscular atrophy. And that success has really catalyzed a lot of interest in industry in developing splice modifying drugs that can change the splicing behavior of specific human genes, of specific exons in specific human genes. But we largely don't know how these drugs work. Understanding how these drugs work is very different than trying to understand how protein targeting drugs work. You can't do the normal assays that you do with proteins. And so the massively parallel splicing assays are turning out to be a very

good way of identifying the sequence elements within gene sequences that determine the specificity of these drugs.

Evelina: And how do we use this information to understand what's going on?

Justin: The other thing though is you know, I focused on the experimental part, but what got me into this was the mathematical modeling. My lab is also, we're pursuing a lot of work to try and figure out why, how do you quantitatively interpret the results of these MAVEs? We're seeing more and more a lot of interest in measuring multiple different protein phenotypes. And of trying to separate out the different functions that the mutations are affecting. And I think quantitative modeling has the potential to do this, but it becomes a lot more sophisticated once you start mixing multiple phenotypes. And so, we're trying to develop both computational methods and just the underlying mathematics needed to support those sorts of investigations.

Evelina: Do you think the field needs to do more of this type of modeling?

Justin: I'm hoping to see is that the field just in general becomes more quantitative and starts leveraging quantitative modeling in order to tease apart the effects of mutations on different molecular phenotypes.

Evelina: Now back to experiments... can you explain the learning curve of switching to the wet-lab?

Justin: I mean, when you're in the lab you're gonna mess up a lot. And, I think what you should do is just give yourself room to mess up a little bit. Don't worry too much about it. You know, it's the successes in the lab that matter, not the failures and no one ever publishes the failures. No one talks about the failures, but it's most of what happens in the lab. I think the smartest thing I've ever done in the lab was to go into the lab.

Evelina: Final question, is there anything you'd like to multiplex outside of the lab?

Justin: Reading papers. Like variants of unknown significance is a major problem. But papers of unknown significance [both laugh] there are many more of those. I'm very interested in many different fields of biology, and I just constantly feel stupid, and I just wish I could just read a lot and just learn a lot more because there's so much excellent work being done by so many people. But it really takes effort to like, learn it and it takes attention and that's the one thing that I feel like I never really have enough time for it's just reading about other people's work.

Evelina: Yeah, that's a great answer, thank you so much!

Alex: Thanks Evelina, so is the conference only for professors or are there many other students like you?

Evelina: I did see some trainees earlier. The Atlas of Variants Effects Alliance in general is very welcoming and it hopes to spotlight trainees. Let me see if I can flag these two speaking over there. Can you please introduce yourselves?

Mateo Cagiada: So I'm Mateo Cagiada, I'm a postdoc at Copenhagen University and Oxford University as well.

Evelina: Do you have any fun stories to tell the audience?

Mateo: So, I've just started my phd and they asked me to analyze a protein. I'm a computational like person. So I have to analyze a protein and I actually didn't know anything about the protein and the protein was called MARK4. And I didn't realize there was a number. So for me, it was MARK. So I analyzed the completely different protein MARK2 instead of MARK4. And I went to an hour-long meeting with the results on a completely different protein. Luckily, for me, like, you know, most of the scientists were nice. So they just laughed and we just, you know, took the chance to look at a different protein. But, you know, I feel like, you know, also if you do stupid stuff in science, usually it's OK. It's not, it's never a mistake to analyze something.

Evelina: Yeah, well at least nothing exploded. What about you Matt?

Matthew Deyell: I'm Matt Deyell from Weill Cornell medicine. And the stupidest thing I've ever done in the lab was I threw activated bromobenzene into the organic waste bin and it exploded.

Evelina: I was just going to say that I microwaved agar with the lid closed but I don't think I can top that.

Kortni: Actually I think I was there to witness that! I think everyone has a fun story that has happened to them in a lab. Are there any others around you Evelina?

Evelina: I think I can talk to one more person before the whole conference begins. Can you please introduce yourself?

Nahum Smith: Yeah so I'm Nahum Smith. I'm a lab manager and research scientist for Dr. Leah Starita at the "U Dub" in Seattle. I joined the Brotman Baty Institute in Genome Sciences back in 2019. And I've been working on saturation genome editing and adjacent projects for the past few years. Took a two year detour into COVID diagnostic testing, but I think everyone did that to some degree. But right now, I mostly kind of assist two different sections of our lab with various, you know, MAVE projects. Yeah, I mostly work on automation in the lab. So like converting a lot of the protocols that were written several years ago by, you know, a grad student here, a postdoc there, and kind of bringing them to scale as we, you know, create more MAVES and create larger ones as well.

Evelina: Back in Toronto Alex has a robot that can do this, but most students just prefer to use their hands. Do you think using robot scientists is the way of the future?

Nahum: Well, I would like it to be easier for everyone to do. So I'd like the prime editors to edit at a higher efficiency. I'd like us to use less cells and tissue culture and still get good read depth. So, like that is what I'm putting a lot of my effort into right now is kind of clearing the way for the people that have ideas about science. So, they're not thinking about what primer sets they need to use or like prepping their libraries and trying to automate the most simple parts of the protocol. So like the difficult things are what people can spend more time doing.

[bell sound in the background to indicate the beginning of the conference]

Evelina: Well there you go! I have to run to catch the first session. I hope this was veryinformative to everybody back home!

Alex: Thanks a lot Evelina, I am sure everybody here will wish they were there. Kortni, do you have anything to add?

Kortni: Yes! Thank you to all that agreed to be interviewed, it was a lot of fun! Today's episode is unusual, but we'll be back for our regular programming until the end of the season, so don't forget to tune in for the next episodes on Variants and Us, where we'll discuss mitochondrial disorders, AI in variant classification and much more!

[Outro music plays]